

ISSUES OF SURVEYING SERVICE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract In the conditions of rapid changes in the world economy, the level of reproduction of real estate objects and property complexes, as a large part of the country's national wealth, is the main global indicator of its effectiveness. This research paper investigates the features of managing commercial facilities and the need to introduce surveying services in the real estate market of Uzbekistan. Property management is a new direction, notion in the real estate market of Uzbekistan. Professional property management is just beginning to emerge as an independent business activity. However, nowadays there are specific trends for the development of this type of business. Usually, owners do not have sufficient resources to effectively manage the property. Even large owners need specialists in the technical expertise of foundations or to monitor the real estate market. Serving companies that have large square meters of management and are constantly in need of such services have the opportunity to hire such specialists.

Keywords: real estate, serving, surveying service, property management, real estate market, real estate management, enterprise and companies, serving concept.

I. Introduction

In the modern world, real estate management plays the role of an absolutely independent type of business, however, in Uzbekistan, this type of business has not yet become widespread. At the same time, the prospects for business development in the field of real estate management are obvious, which means it's time to pay attention to this issue. It's no secret that real estate is one of the most popular investment resources. Large enterprises and successful companies invest their profits in the purchase of real estate, thus ensuring the safety of funds. At the same time, few owners take into account the fact that real estate, like any other asset, requires constant attention. And with the proper level of management activity, it can not only save the invested funds, but also bring significant profit [3]. Property management is a novelty in the real estate market of Uzbekistan and many potential clients simply do not understand the essence and purpose of this type of service. As a rule, they do not imagine the possibility of effective use of real estate and management technologies to increase its profitability and market value.

As foreign practice shows, today in the field of commercial real estate management it is possible to achieve high efficiency through the use of the serving concept. Surveying is considered to be an effective tool that enables the optimal organization of real estate management. When implementing the serving concept, the serving company plays a major role. A surveying company is a company specialized in the professional management of real estate. As a rule, the surveying company is not the owner of the properties it manages. He signs a management agreement with the owner of the facility and makes every effort to achieve the goals.

In Uzbekistan, professional property management is just beginning to stand out as an independent type of entrepreneurial activity. But, referring to domestic practice, it is difficult to say that today there are specific trends for the development of this type of business. There are three main directions in the formation of management companies.

The first direction is explained by the fact that real estate firms, which began with the services of finding potential tenant clients for owners of large buildings and premises, gradually began to perform some functions of real estate management.

The second direction implies that construction companies, upon completion of construction, take on the functions of operating companies and reach the level of a management company by increasing the range of functions they provide.

The third direction is connected with the fact that the owners of large real estate objects create structural departments for their management, after which they turn into independent management companies [1].

The following factors can promote to create obstacles to the development of management companies in the modern world:

- lack of tested and open standards, as well as methods of professional property management;
- lack of experienced professionals in the field of real estate management;
- underdevelopment of real estate management infrastructure;
- lack of availability of independent and professional property management consultants

In the conditions of rapid changes in the world economy, the level of reproduction of real estate objects and property complexes, as a large part of the country's national wealth, is the main global indicator of its effectiveness. For example, "In developed countries, the housing fund makes up 20% to 45% of the national wealth that is reproduced in the country. If we consider all types of real estate, including land and property complexes, then this figure is 70-80%» [1]. In this regard, effective management of real estate reproduction processes on the basis of modern economic concepts, including management of servicing and professional development of real estate objects, can be indicated as the most important and urgent task. The relevance of this issue can be explained by the fact that the Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors was established in London in 1881, and today more than 125,000 professional surveyors are working in it in more than 150 countries of the world. It can be seen that this type of activity is expected to spread more widely to the countries of the world and the process of providing surveying services will be accelerated.

Conducted extensive scientific research on the improvement of the management system of surveying services in the world real estate market. In particular, the complexity of real estate, the variety of opportunities for its movement in the market, covering all stages of real estate life cycle; requires the need to establish a system that creates a unified planning system of performance and liquidity target indicators for various real estate objects, and provides effective real estate management. In the current conditions, the study of the specific scientific-methodical foundations of the management of servicing services in the real estate market, defining the main directions, developing the management mechanisms of services, clarifying the spectrum of servicing services are among the main scientific trends.

As an integral part of the economy of Uzbekistan, comprehensive measures are being implemented to manage real estate objects. In 2017-2021, the Action Strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines important tasks such as "creating an effective competitive environment for economic sectors and gradually reducing monopoly in the market of products and services" [2].

The result of this is a low level of property management and the disinterest of owners in cooperation with professional management companies. The core business of a surveying company consists of relationships with property owners, maintenance and utility contractors, and the government as a market regulator. Relations with real estate owners are built on the basis of a contract and a real estate management program. Under the agreement, the owner transfers the object to the management of the surveying company for a certain period, and the surveying company, in turn, undertakes to manage the property in the interests of the owner. The transfer of a property to

the management of a surveying company does not give it the right of ownership. The management agreement specifies the forms and reporting mechanisms of the surveying company. The management program is developed by the surveying company based on the analysis of the current state and the results of forecasting the dynamics during the management of the property. The management program provides a list of activities in all areas of property management, as well as a budget for income and expenses.

The advantage of a surveying company over an independent type of management is manifested in achieving better results. It is not always possible for the owner to effectively manage his real estate. Firstly, surveying companies have the proper experience and guarantee objectivity; secondly, they solve the problem of personnel selection; thirdly, they provide optimization of operating costs in the operation of real estate [1].

Usually, owners do not have sufficient resources to effectively manage the property. Even the largest owners once a year need specialists in the technical expertise of foundations or to monitor the real estate market. At this time, surveying companies that have large square meters in management and are constantly in need of such services have the opportunity to hire such specialists.

As time passes, the goals of the owners change. So, as a result of the expansion of the main economic activity, commercial real estate begins to be used for operational purposes, and the need for personnel involved in renting out temporarily empty buildings is changing accordingly. Due to the large number of clients of the surveying company, it is easier for him to get used to the change in the composition [11].

Of course, in some cases, the owner of commercial real estate can independently manage the facilities. As a rule, in such cases they are characterized by the following factors:

- such objects are intended for commercial use for no more than two years;
- such objects are an integral part of a larger property of the owner used for operational purposes [9];
- these are objects about which complete and timely information is always available;
- such facilities do not require the preparation of separate contracts for operation, utility and maintenance;
- there is no need for reconstruction and major repairs in such facilities;
- the existing use case of the property complies with the principle of the best and most efficient use;

II. Literature Review

In the system of markets, the real estate market and the types of services provided in it, in particular, real estate management, are relatively newly formed in the republic. There are several research works written by foreign and Uzbek scientists. In particular, with the management of real estate objects. scientific works by foreign scientists such as Edj. Mc-Lean, N. Ordway, Dj. Friedman, G. Harrison, Dj. Eckert, Donald Dj. Trump, A. Zuckerman, Dj. D. Blevins, GB. Eddredlar and others [3, 4].

The scientists of independent states such as - A.N. Asaul, I.T. Balabanov, L.P. Belykh, V.I. Busov, A.Z. Galeev, P.G. Grabovoy, C.B. Gribovskoy, V.A. Goremykin, A. G. Gryaznova, V. V. Ivanov, I. I. Mazur, S. N. Maksimov, A. B. Marchenko, E. S. Ozerov, N. G. Olderogge, M. L. Razu, V. M. Rutgeiser, E.I.Tarasevich, L.N.Tepman, M.A.Fedotova, O.K.Khan, V.D.Shapiro, H.A.shcherbakova, V.Z.Chernyak., S.A.Lomakina work and investigate the research on clarification of the issue of management of real estate object [5] .

Uzbek scientists such as M.A. Ikramov, M. Mirakhmedov, R.I. Nurimbetov, B.Yu. Khodiev, B.B. Berkinov, V.U. Yodgorov, Sh.A. Isamukhamedova, T.A.Khasanov, D. Ya. Butunov and others studied scientific research works on Some problems of managing real estate objects in Uzbekistan [6].

The above-mentioned foreign and Uzbek scientists have conducted many researches in the field of real estate market, management and evaluation of real estate objects. At the same time, the issues

of introduction of surveying services and improvement of professional management in the national real estate market have not been researched as an independent research object.

III. Research Methodology

While conducting the research, systematic approach, statistical and economic analysis, comparison, analysis and synthesis methods, expert assessment, scientific forecast and other methods were used.

The scientific novelty of the research is as follows:

- the concept of "surveying services" has been improved as a set of activities carried out by business entities in order to achieve effective operation of the real estate object and based on the application of a comprehensive approach to its management;
- the organizational and legal basis for the introduction of surveying services for the professional management of residential and commercial real estate objects was improved based on the development of the temporary regulation "On surveying services for the management of real estate objects";
- it is based on the organization of the construction of student residences on the basis of public-private partnership and the organization of surveying services with the help of an outsourcing contract for the use of buildings; Within the framework of investment programs in Uzbekistan, the forecast indicators of the effectiveness of the student accommodation management system until 2027 have been determined.

IV. Analysis and results

Based on the scientific results obtained on improving the management of servicing services in the real estate market:

The proposal to improve the concept of "surveying services" as a set of activities implemented by business entities in order to achieve effective operation of the real estate object and based on the application of a comprehensive approach to its management was introduced into the educational process of the Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Construction (2020 of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Order No. 285-294 of May 4). As a result, a study guide entitled "Basics of surveying in the real estate market" was created, which fully describes surveying services, their history, and their importance in the real estate market, and provided an opportunity for specialists to develop skills in surveying services;

The proposal to improve the organizational and legal basis for the introduction of surveying services for the professional management of residential and commercial real estate objects was introduced into the practice of the Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Housing and Communal Services of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2020 of the Ministry of Housing and Communal Services of the Republic of Uzbekistan Reference No. 02/04-4571 dated December 2; Document No. 1324/16-03 of the Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 13, 2020;). As a result, a temporary regulation "On surveying services for the management of real estate objects" was developed, and it is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Management of Multi-apartment Houses in the cities of Yakkasaray district, Jizzakh and Margilon of the city of Tashkent" No. 64 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2020 was used in the project of the decision "On conducting a legal experiment" regarding the approval of norms;

The proposal to organize the construction of student residences on the basis of public-private partnership and to organize surveying services with the help of an outsourcing contract for the use of buildings was introduced into the activities of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Decision No. 89-04 of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 16, 2020 reference number 1030). As a result, it was possible to organize the construction of student residences on the basis of public-private partnership and to organize the use of buildings on the basis of surveying. Within the framework of investment programs in Uzbekistan, the proposal to determine the forecast

indicators of the efficiency of the management system of student accommodation by the organizations serving students until 2027 was introduced into the activity of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (Reference No. 89-04-1030 of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 16, 2020). The implementation of this proposal made it possible to obtain additional income and reduce the total operating costs by 20% based on the services provided in return for transferring the operation of the student residential building to the servicing organization.

Analysis of the results of services offered by specialized companies. In order to identify deficiencies in management in order to conduct a qualitative examination of the results of real estate management, invite a consulting firm in the field of real estate management as an independent expert. If the above conditions or at least one of them are not met, it is advisable for the owner to think about transferring the property to the management of a specialized surveying company.

Using the services of a surveying company gives the owner a number of advantages. In this case, the owners:

- firstly, they receive specific information about the strengths and weaknesses of their object and an action plan for managing the object in question;
- secondly, they receive income from optimizing the operating costs of their property;
- thirdly, they are released from the obligation to solve current problems related to the maintenance and operation of real estate.

In Uzbekistan, these services today require systematization in the real estate management services market. All participants in the real estate market should have a clear idea of the advisability of timely contacting companies providing surveying services. If at least one of the properties presented in the Figure is determined in a real estate object, then we can assume that there is a need for the services of a surveying company [14]. If the object meets at least one of the above, then it is advisable for the owner to develop an option for transferring the management of the property to a surveying company [9].

The surveying company has the ability to reduce all the costs of its customers associated with the operation of the proposed buildings, by performing specific functions. It manages a portfolio of properties with a variety of properties. As a result, clients of the surveying company can transform their property into the one they need at the moment. Surveying companies can manage not only existing objects in circulation, but also objects ready for commissioning. This makes it possible to take into account the personal choice of planning in the process of working with the client. Such companies can take on the management of business centers that have the highest degree of logistics, a range of professional services, an expanded infrastructure, stores and chains of shopping complexes, as well as free-standing objects for various purposes.

The attractiveness of real estate has significantly increased since market relations became an integral part of the economy of Uzbekistan. There are a number of reasons for the growing interest in real estate management as a type of independent professional activity. Among them, it is possible to single out the reasons of the owners conditioned by commercial goals. Issues of obtaining income from the operation of the object and the possibility of its maximization are the main reasons why real estate owners make a decision to use the services of professional market participants.

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Real estate management is a risk-based and profit-oriented activity during the use of ownership, use and disposal rights [6]. The complexity and versatility of real estate, its circulation in the market and the variety of opportunities for its use make it necessary to create an effective system of real estate management. Such a system should cover all stages of the life cycle, create a

single planned system of results and liquidity target indicators for various real estate objects, and ensure the effectiveness of management forms.

Using the concept of surveying in real estate management is an innovative solution, and a systematic approach is its basis. Surveying (ingl. survey - study, inspection) - the use of a systematic approach to the development and management of real estate; includes all types of planning (strategic, operative) for the purpose of real estate activity, as well as activities related to conducting technical and economic expertise of real estate, ensuring maximum efficiency in real estate management [7]. Specific aspects of the types of business activities implemented in the real estate market of the Republic of Uzbekistan can be presented in the form of table 1.

Table 1

Specific characteristics of the types of business activities offered in the market of services in the field of movement of real estate objects and their management

Comparison factors	Real estate management (surveying) activity	Development activity	Real estate activity
Field of activity	Business activity on the provision of services		
Structure of services	Services for complex, systematic management of real estate at all stages of its life cycle	Services for the preparation and implementation of investment projects in the field of Real estate and monitoring the construction of Real estate objects.	Mediation and information services in the implementation of operations with Real estate objects
The main functions of companies providing this type of service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collection and analysis of information on Real estate objects; -Real estate assessment, examination and initiation; - preparation and implementation of projects for construction and modernization of buildings; -Real estate sale and lease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating a real estate object; - working out a business concept; - delivery of the finished object 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Selection of Real estate objects; - organization of showing objects; -checking documents confirming the lessor's rights; - helping to draw up a lease agreement <p style="text-align: center;">Serving</p>

The surveying company has the opportunity to reduce all the costs of its customers associated with the operation of the proposed buildings, through the performance of specific functions. It manages a portfolio of properties with a variety of properties. As a result, the clients of the service company can transform their real estate, in such what they need at the moment. Surveying companies can manage not only existing facilities in turn over, but also objects ready for commissioning. This makes it possible to take into account personal choice planning in the process of working with the client. Such companies can take for the management of business centers that have the highest degree of logistics services, a range of professional services, expanded infrastructure, shops and networks of shopping malls, as well as separate objects for various purposes.

Having studied serving as a form of professional and independent management

real estate objects, as well as, as a result of generalization of information about the activities companies offering serving services, the following definition is given to the concept "serving services": serving services are a set of activities performed by business entities and based on integrated approach to real estate management, the purpose of these services is maximizing the possible income of the owner in a particular place and at a particular time, achievement of the effective functioning of the object in the future [3].

The activities of service companies can also be in demand in such cases like, bankruptcy, financial crises, management against crisis, recovery from crisis and subsequent financial recovery. According to the concept of serving, investors acquire the debtor enterprise through an auction and transfer it to specialists for management [4]. The application of serving principles can provide financial recovery of debtor enterprises. Basic rules of management and operation of real estate can be used in the financial recovery of the enterprise. At bankrupt enterprises, there are always real estate objects in the form of buildings and facilities that are not used in the main production. The company must keep real estate, which is an additional factor for financial difficulties, because it can be useful for small businesses. In the process of reorganization Bankruptcy activities usually transfer assets to a newly created legal entity where they are effectively used. These are the features of serving services that, apparently, can be in demand even in times of crisis. Using the services of surveying organizations provides a number of advantages to property owners. Firstly, they are ownership obtains accurate information about the strengths and weaknesses of its facilities and a plan of action for the management of this facility; secondly, operating expenses related to their own real estate earns from optimization; thirdly, they own real estate solving current problems related to storage and operation will be freed from necessity. These services are real estate management services requires systematization in the market. All market participants when to contact companies that provide servicing services, they should have a clear idea about the appropriateness of the purpose.

Real estate management is clearly related to each other, lack of services to meet the basic needs of property owners, the number and types of services, the only one that determines the processes requires the creation of a system. All types of real estate management services and covering all stages of the life cycle of the real estate object need. Therefore, the service of the real estate management system content based on services, it was considered appropriate to analyze the impact. Scientific and methodological problems in the object being studied in scientific work analysis of practical aspects and scientific-organizational management to define specific ways to improve the methods in the future. The initial number of specialists was 80 people questionnaires were sent, 23 of them participated in the expert evaluation did. Group error detection with 23 experts in this graph, the average group error does not exceed 0.5, which fully meets the requirements of the study.

V. CONCLUSION

The scientific and practical results obtained in the study are based on a systematic approach to the problem. The concept of the mechanism is considered professional management of various real estate objects in general. The need for such a mechanism stemmed from the need increasing the number of real estate in the country, the pace of modernization and development of economic sectors.

Based on the concept of improvement proposed in the dissertation real estate management based on surveying services are made scientifically methodological and practical conclusions on the following key aspects:

When disclosing the concept of "surveying services", the following are defined moments:

1. Firstly, it is a set of measures taken by business entities to achieve the efficient operation of the facility and based on the application an integrated approach to real estate management; Secondly, this covers different stages of the life cycle of the property; Thirdly, it is a type of management activity aimed at increasing in the market value of the property or security of maximum profitability.

2. Serving services provide professional, comprehensive and systematic property management. Their distinguishing feature is that the management of real estate is carried out in the interests of owner and aimed at achieving a clear result. At the same time in the process of providing serving services provides for a clear division of functions between the owner and the managing organization.

3. It is no longer enough for homeowners to simply develop a concept or business plan for the successful implementation of projects in modern conditions;

4. Since most real estate objects in modern conditions managed by the owners, there are difficulties in finding buyers when entering the market. It is substantiated that in order to become effective in real estate management tool and improve its efficiency.

5. Real estate management is not well organized and the introduction of services should be carried out gradually, in certain sequence.

Based on the results of the expert assessment, the need for implementation of service services in the real estate management system. Currently, due to the lack of sufficient conditions for development of surveying organizations and regulation of their activities in practice, the services are not specified. Development of management activities in the local real estate market depends on the creation of surveying organizations, the preparation of regulatory legal documents regulating their activities, as well as from the development organizational and economic mechanism for the implementation of surveying services.

REFERENCES

1. Surveying services and professional real estate development: theory, practice: monograph: in 3 parts. Part 1. Management module of the surveying system and its development / scientific. ed. P. G. Grabovoi; Ministry of Education and Science Ross. Federation, FGBOU VPO "Mosk. state builds. un-t. - Moscow: MGSU, 2012. - p. 264.

2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan". //lex.uz/

3. McLean E.J., Eldred G.W. Investment in real estate. Per. from English. - M.: ID William, 2007 - 416 p. ISBN 5-8459-1144, Tepman L.N. Real estate valuation: textbook. allowance. - M.: UNITI-DANA, 2007. - p. 463. ISBN 978-5-238-01152-3, Trump, Donald J. Think Like a Billionaire: Everything You Need to Know About Success, Real Estate, and Life in General: trans. from English. Donald J. Trump with Meredith MacIver. - M.: Alpina Business Book, 2005. ISBN 5-9614-0244-4, Friedman J., Ordway Nick. Analysis and evaluation of income-generating real estate / per. from English. M: business. 1997.

4. Friedman, Jack P. Dictionary of Real Estate Terms. 7 ed. - Barron's educational series, inc., 2008. ISBN: 0-7641-3936-3. ISBN (EAN): 978-0-7641-3936-9, Gary W. Eldred The Beginner's Guide to Real Estate Investing. - John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2004. ISBN: 047164711X. Gerri Willis The SmartMoney Guide to Real Estate Investing. - Wiley, 2004. ISBN: 0-471-64748-9. ISBN: 978-0-471-64748-5. Loren K. Keim The Fundamentals of Selling Commercial Real Estate. - Infinity Publishing, 2008.

5. Asaul A.N., Karasev A.V. Real estate economics. - M.: MIKHiS, 2001, Belykh L.P. Building a real estate portfolio. - M.: Finance and statistics, 1999. - 262 p. ISBN 5-279-02104-0, Busov V.I. Essence and place of value management in company management // Valuation Issues. - 2007, No. 4, Galeev A.Z. Real estate management - a professional approach [Electronic resource]. - Electron, yes. - Access mode: http://www.rentasystem.ru/index6.files/bar_page2.htm, Goremykin V.A. Economics and real estate management: a textbook. - M.: MGIU, 2007. - 345 p. ISBN 978-5-2760-1081-6, Reisberg, B.A. Modern Economic Dictionary / B.A. Reisberg, L.Sh. Lozovsky, E.B. Starodubtsev. - 6th ed., revised. and additional - Moscow: INFRA-M, 2017. - 512 p. - (Library of dictionaries "INFRA-M"). - ISBN 978-5-16-105386-7, Ivanov V.V., Khan O.K. Property management. - M.: INFRA-M, 2007. - 446 p. - (National projects). ISBN 978-5-16-003071-5, Mazur I.I., Shapiro V.D., Olderogge N.G. Development. Series: Modern business education. - M.: Publisher: Economics, 2004, 528 p. ISBN 5-282-02312-1, Tarasevich E.I. Real estate management.

St. Petersburg: MKS, 2006. ISBN 5-901810-10-4, Financial management: theory and practice: Textbook / Ed. E.S. Stoyanova. 5th ed., revised. and additional - M.: Publishing house "Perspective", 2004, Chernyak V.Z. Property management. - M.: Exam, 2006. ISBN: 5-472-01600-2.

6. Ikramov M., Mirakhmedov M., Yodgorov V., Mirdjalilova D. Real estate economy: Textbook/ Prof. M.M. Mirakhmedov and prof. Under the general editorship of M.A. Ikramov. - Tashkent: VneshInvestProm, 2018. - 424 pages; Toychiev N.J., Mirkhoshimov A.M., Plakhtiy K.A. Fundamentals of Real Estate Appraisal. Study guide. - Tashkent: Adolat, 2000.; M. Ziyaeva. Structural features of the services market in Uzbekistan. Business Expert. #3. (123) – 2018; Yodgorov V.U., Butunov D.Ya. Economy and management of housing and communal economy. Textbook. - T.: TAQI, 2011; Alimov R.H., Berkinov B.B., Kravchenko A.N., Khodiev B.Yu. Real estate appraisal. - T.: Science, 2005.; Sh.A. Isamukhamedova, V.U. Yodgorov. Real estate management and expertise. Study guide. - T.: Center for Architecture, Construction, Integration and Innovation. 2011 94 p.; T.A. Hasanov. Improvement of the private housing stock management system in Uzbekistan. Abstract. "Academy Publishing Center", 2019.

7. Knyazeva, N. V. (2017). Industrial real estate management in the context of life cycle theory. *Bulletin of the South Ural State University. Series: Economics and Management*, 11 (2), 36-41.

8. Ivanova, M., A., & Kudryavtseva, V. A. (2017). Serving professional management system. *Transport infrastructure of the Siberian region*, 2, 66-71.

9. Vladimirovna-Bredikhina, N. (2017). Basic principles of production-and-technical potential capacity formation in the construction industry of a region. *Journal of Applied Engineering Science*, 15(4), 495-497.

10. Makarova, M.I., & Mukhatinova, R.N. (2016). Serving as an effective tool for managing real estate. *Social Sciences*, 1 (5-1), 19-23.

11. Mirjalilova D. Sh. Ways to improve real estate management based on surveying services. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 01 (81), 156-162. <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS> (ISRA = 4.971, GIF = 0.564, ICRV = 6.630 OAJI = 0.350)

12. Ziyaev M.K., Mirdjalilova D.Sh. Servicing services in the real estate market. Scientific and practical magazine "Architecture Construction Design" 2017. No. 3-4. p. 182-184. (08.00.00 #2).

13. Djumaniyazova M. Yu. Prospective development of electronic commerce in Uzbekistan// *Economics and business: theory and practice*. 2018. No. 6. P. 63-66.

14. Overview of the market for management services in the field of residential and commercial real estate [Electronic resource]. - Access mode: <http://www.estimation.ru/ru/analytics/2009/05/28-2-4>.

15. Dmitry Lebed. Our credo is jewelry work with real estate. [Electronic resource]. - Access mode: <https://www.uzdaily.uz/articles-id-8366.htm>

16. Asaul A.N., Karasev A.V. Real estate economics. – M.: MIKHIS, 2001.